

Deciphering AI for the Life Sciences

Ben Goudey

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Ben Goudey: who am I?

- AI Tech Lead: Figuring how AI is used in life-sciences, what the barriers are and how BioCommons can help to communities to overcome these

Academia

Postdoc
(23/24)

Postdoc (21/22)

PhD, Comp Sci
(2016)

Industrial Research

Research
Scientist, 13-21

PhD, Comp Sci
(2016)

Now Data61

The AI Hype in Life Sciences

New AI Tool Uses Routine Blood Tests to Predict Immunotherapy Response for Many Cancers

By Ian Demsky, Monday, January 6, 2025

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Pangea Biomed's AI Predicts Cancer Treatment Responses from Tumor Images

By Jonathan D. Grinstein, PhD July 3, 2024

Today's webinar: what we'll cover

- Different definitions of AI and why understanding them is useful
- How different types of AI are used in life sciences and how they relate to each other
- Key considerations when thinking about using AI in research

What we'll not cover

- No in-depth methods or coding
- No details around implementation, coding or infrastructure
- Detailed descriptions or analysis of methods or models
- No worked examples of how to apply AI models to your data

Why should I care what AI means

- **Improve Collaboration:** Get everyone on the same page when discussing AI-related ideas
- **Critical Literature Review:** Helps you sift through articles and claims more accurately.
- **Tailor grants or ethics applications:** Use the right language to impress (or not frighten) review committees.
- **Understand Problem Fit:** Different AI techniques solve different types of challenges and have different data/compute requirements—this is necessary for effective planning.

A Very High-Level Definition of AI

“Technology that allows a computer to do something that normally require human intelligence”

But practically speaking this is not very helpful

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Linear regression

Human-like intelligence

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How AI definition has changed over time

- <Add a timeline to talk to quickly>
- 1960s: First AI hype wave (symbolic AI, expert systems)
- 1980s: Another wave, still largely rule-based
- 1990s–2000s: Emergence of “classical” Machine Learning (SVMs, random forests, simpler neural nets)
- 2013–2020: Deep Learning explosion (computer vision, speech recognition breakthroughs)
- 2020–Now: Large Language Models & Generative AI (e.g. GPT, AlphaFold)

When People Say “AI,” They Might Mean...

Artificial General Intelligence

Machine learning

Deep learning

Large-language models and Generative AI

When People Say “AI,” They Might Mean...

AI = Machine Learning

What is Machine learning

Definition: class of algorithms designed to learn patterns in data that will hold on new data (i.e are *generalizable*)

Traditional programming

Write a program with **explicit rules** to follow:

```
if genome contains mutation 1
then mark risk
if genome contains mutation 2,
then mark no risk
if genome contains ...
if genome contains ...
```

Machine Learning

Algorithms that take data and **learn** to predict an outcome

1. **Guess risk from mutations**
2. **Classify** genomes based on guess strategy
3. **Change strategy** to reduce error
4. **Repeat from 1.**

Is it just statistics? Good question...

- In **ML**, goal is **prediction** – less concern about why it works (interpretation)
 - Focus on ability to predict on data **not seen** by the model
- In **statistics**, goal is **attribution**, understanding the relationships between variables of interest
 - Focus on strength of associations when looking at all data at once
- But honestly, its a bit of a blurred area
 - Highly recommend *Breiman (2001) “Statistical Modeling: The Two Cultures”* for a clear discussion on the differences

Classes of machine learning techniques

<https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.05433>

Classes of machine learning techniques

But many more exist

- Reinforcement learning
- Semi-supervised learning
- Transfer learning
- etc

arxiv.org/abs/1910.05433

Supervised learning

Given:

- A matrix of data $\mathbf{X}_{n \times p}$
- A vector of labels \mathbf{y}_n

learn a function $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{X})$ that takes \mathbf{X} and predicts \mathbf{y}

More observations, better fit

Classic example is linear regression

$$y = \sum \beta_i x_i$$

Linear regression being fit with increasing number of observations

Evaluation is critical

If we have two datasets:

- Train model on one
- Test on remaining

If we only have a single dataset, we can simulate two datasets by splitting the data into parts

- Cross-validation

Data I have today

Data I want my model to make predictions on

Data I have today

???

Lots of types of models, different characteristics

Regression based

Tree-based / Non-parametric

Ensemble models

Neural network

Neural network

Note: This is the most maths in the whole talk
Simple NN is like regression

Output

Linear combination of inputs

$$\hat{y} = g \left(w_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m w_i x_i \right)$$

Bias

Non-linear activation function

Neural network (simplified)

A model like this is **almost the same** as regression.

Can still only model fairly linear functions.

Hidden layer

Size=1

Neural network - more neurons, more flexibility

A model like this is a lot **more flexible** than regression.

Can model non-linear functions. Flexibility grows with hidden layer size.

Key challenge: want a model that is sensitive but not confused by noise

Too simple!
(underfitting)

Sweet spot

Too complex!
(overfitting)

What are the requirements for training a model?

	Machine learning
Sample size	100-10,000
Compute need	Local laptop
# of parameters	10-10million

Once the model is fit, making prediction is much computationally cheaper

How is machine learning used in the life-sciences?

Common when dealing with small sample sizes ($n < 10,000$)

Lipidomic signature to predict risk (ridge-regression)

Lipidomic Risk Score to Enhance
Cardiovascular Risk Stratification for
Primary Prevention

Jingqin Wu, PhD,^{a,b,*} Corey Giles, PhD,^{a,b,c,*} Aleksandar Dakic, PhD,^a Habtamu B. Beyene, PhD,^{a,b,c,d}

Leading Alzheimer's blood test use a simple linear regression

Highly accurate blood test for Alzheimer's disease is similar or superior to clinical cerebrospinal fluid tests

[Nicolas R. Barthélemy](#), [Gemma Salvadó](#), [Suzanne E. Schindler](#), [Yingxin He](#), [Shorena Janelidze](#), [Lyduine E.](#)

GATK's "Variant recalibration score" is an ML model trained on a few thousand samples

Summary: Machine learning

Machine learning = algorithms that learn patterns from data that hold on unseen data

Primary goal is to guess correctly on data not seen by the model

Lots of complications but at least a lot can be done on your own computer (at least most of the time).

AI = Deep Learning

Deep learning

Neural networks with multiple stacked layers

Deep learning as a feature extractor

With the right data and the right set up, DL can derive robust features from very structured data.

Deep learning as a feature extractor

Imagine we need to predict faces, what features might be extracted?

Low level features

Edges, dark spots

First layers

Mid level features

Eyes, ears, nose

Middle layers

High level features

Facial structure

End layers

Images from MIT 6.S191 Introduction to Deep Learning
© Alexander Amini and Ava Amini, MIT Introduction to Deep Learning, IntroToDeepLearning.com

But Ben, didn't you say NNs have been around forever? What changed?

Data: People realized more data is the best way to get a robust model

Compute: GPUs became powerful and graphics processing and neural networks both rely on matrix operations

Network Architecture

Describes how we configure network size, connections, summarisation functions to suit the data and problem.

<p>Convolution NN</p> <p>Imaging, Spatial</p>	
<p>Graph NN</p> <p>Social networks, chemical structures</p>	

Fine-tuning: re-using learnt representations on new tasks

Model 1. Lots of pet images. Learn feature representations that can distinguish cats and dogs.

Model 2. Few brain images. **Re-use model 1** feature extractor and only **fine-tune (tweak)** the final parts for segmenting the brain

What are the requirements for training deep learning?

	Machine learning	Deep Learning
Sample size	100-10,000	10,000-100Millions
Compute need	Local laptop	1-many GPU
# of parameters	10-10million	100 Millions-100s Billions

Once the model is fit, making prediction is much computationally cheaper

How is deep learning used in the life-sciences?

Anything imaging!

AI-assisted breast-cancer screening may reduce unnecessary testing

Using AI to help doctors read mammograms reduces follow-up testing without missing cancer cases, simulation shows

Multi-omics

scRNA-seq annotation

Interpreting single-cell and spatial omics data using deep neural network training dynamics

[Jonathan Karin](#), [Reshef Mintz](#), [Barak Raveh](#)

[Nature Computational Science](#) 4, 941–954 (2024) | [Cite this article](#)

Summary: Deep learning

Deep Learning = a specialized category of ML, based on neural networks

Powerful for structured data (images, text, sequences) if dataset & compute scale permit

Complexity in setup and interpretation

AI = Large Language
Models

Large Language Models

- **Huge** deep learning models to understand patterns in **sequence** data
 - and often designed to generate sequences as well
- Text but also audio, protein, nucleic acids, images etc

Given the sequence of input **tokens** (e.g. words), LLMs predict the most probable word to come next.

- “*autocomplete on steroids*”

Why are they so clever? Data!

Its mostly just more data!

LLMs are taking in all possible documents, code, reddit threads, focums and learning a compressed representation (the model)

The abilities of these models surprised everyone!!

Clever trick: the data doesn't need labels

One key breakthrough is that LLMs don't rely on lots of curated data

Instead, they explicitly focus on learning, for each word, which surrounding words are most important (attention)

- Resulting model learns a rich representation of the structure and inherent patterns in the given “language”

What are the requirements for training deep learning?

	Machine learning	Deep Learning	LLMs
Sample size	100-10,000	10,000-100Millions	Millions to Billions
Compute need	Local laptop	1-many GPU	1 GPU - Data center of GPU for several months
# of parameters	10-10million	100 Millions-100s Billions	Billions - Trillions

Once the model is fit, making prediction is much computationally cheaper

AlphaFold: a breakthrough in protein structure prediction

Protein sequence (1D)
(amino-acids are words)

Protein structure (3D)

AlphaFold: a breakthrough in protein structure prediction

2.5x better than all competing solutions in CASP 14 (2020)

Won Nobel Prize

AlphaFold: still has limitations!

Data comes from Protein Data Bank, full of protein sequence and crystal structures

BUT - what about classes of proteins who structure couldn't be derived previously

Sometimes it works. sometimes it doesn't

Also AlphaFold confidently makes mistakes across many protein types

What is GenAI?

Definition: Models that can be used to simulate new data, not just make predictions

What are foundation models

Definition: A catch-all term for really big models, often LLMs, trained on massive amounts of data and that can be tweaked for downstream tasks

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Definition: A catch-all term for really big models, often LLMs, trained on massive amounts of data and that can be tweaked for downstream tasks

A foundation model for generalizable disease detection from retinal images

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06555-x>

Received: 5 December 2022

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Mateo G. Lozano^{2,5}, Peter Woodward-Court^{1,2,6}, Yuka Kihara^{7,8}, UK Biobank Eye & Vision

Where does ChatGPT fit in?

Definition: Specialized LLMs - given a **prompt** (*a set of text from a user*), these models generate **coherent and relevant text**.

Can be quite wrong (**hallucination**) but is often surprisingly good.

Where does ChatGPT fit in?

What time is it now?

Reasoned for a couple of seconds >

I don't have access to real-time data. Please check a clock or your device for the current time.

can you use python to check the time now?

Reasoned for a couple of seconds >

The current local time is: **2025-03-16 00:27:59**.

Keep in mind this reflects the time on the system where the code is executed. [\[>-\]](#)

Where does ChatGPT fit in?

How many times does the letter R in the word raspberrry?

The word "rasprberry" appears to be a misspelling of "raspberry".

If you meant "rasprberry", it contains **three R's**.

If you meant "raspberry", it contains **two R's**.

Where does ChatGPT fit in?

How many times does the letter R in the word raspberrry?

Reasoned for 11 seconds

It looks like the word in your question is spelled "**raspberrry**" (with an extra "r"). If we count the "r" letters in exactly that spelling — **r-a-s-p-r-b-e-r-r-y** — we find:

1. r (1st letter)
2. r (5th letter)
3. r (8th letter)
4. r (9th letter)

So there are **4** instances of the letter "r" in "raspberrry."

(For reference, the standard spelling "raspberry" has 3 "r"s.)

Concluding thoughts

What do we mean when we talk about AI?

Its context-dependent! But often means either:

Machine learning: wide class of algorithms designed to learn patterns in data that are generalizable

Deep learning: complex neural networks that can be adapted for specific types of data

Large language models (LLMs): a type of deep learning model designed for sequences and training on mountains of data that can simulate new sequences

But could also be

ChatGPT/AI powered chatbots: Specialized LLMs that repond to prompts (input text)

GenAI: Any large model (often LLM) that can generate new data

Broad questions

Are LLMs or other AI intelligent?

- no or at least not in the traditional sense

I don't care about predicting things, I want to understand the biology

- These are broadly predictive models, understanding causal relationships can be tricky

Lots of models, what should I trust?

- Requires an understanding of the model, the input data and the domain

There's an AI-based tool I want to use online, what should I consider

- Is it "right" to send your data?

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